

ACHIEVING HIGH-INTEGRITY VOLUNTARY CLIMATE ACTION

D6.1 – Data Management Plan (DMP)

WP6 – Project management &
governance

26/06/2024

www.achieveproject.eu

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Disclaimer

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Responsible Author	Kaustubh Thapa			RU
Contributors	Leads of all project partners			
Reviewer(s)	Georgios Xexakis (HOL); Birka Wicke (RU)			
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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the Description of Action (DoA)

There are no changes with respect to the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable will serve as a reference for data management among consortium partners.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

The ACHIEVE project, funded by the European Union, aims to enhance and scale high-integrity voluntary climate action to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050. The project involves a diverse consortium of partners and focuses on generating scientific insights into the effectiveness and integrity of voluntary climate actions. It examines carbon credits, assesses impacts, and analyzes how policies can support these actions.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) adheres to Horizon Europe guidelines and outlines how data will be collected, managed, and shared. It emphasises data integrity and reuse, with a commitment to making data as open as possible while protecting sensitive information. Data will be stored in secure repositories like Zenodo and Radboud University's servers, with public access facilitated through various platforms. Key types of data include quantitative and qualitative information on voluntary climate actions collected through surveys, interviews, and existing databases. The project ensures data interoperability and adherence to GDPR, focusing on transparency and reusability. Ethical guidelines and secure data management practices are maintained by all partners, ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and standards. This living document is created with inputs from all project partners and is expected to be modified as necessary.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

Creating and finalising this document is proof.

Achieving High Integrity Voluntary Climate Action

Project abstract:

In recent years, a wide array of non-state and subnational actors have made an unprecedented number of voluntary climate commitments. These voluntary climate actions aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and build climate resilience and are crucial for lowering risks of exceeding warming limits. However, the full potential of voluntary climate action can only be realised when integrity-related concerns are overcome.

ACHIEVE aims to identify opportunities to strengthen and scale up high-integrity voluntary climate action towards achieving net-zero emissions by mid-century. The project will generate transformative and timely scientific insights on the role, effectiveness and integrity of voluntary climate action, including carbon credits; assess the integrity and impacts of such action; analyse how policies and regulations and high-integrity voluntary climate action can strengthen each other; and use scientific findings to support the scaling up of high-integrity voluntary action. This will be achieved through a highly inter- and transdisciplinary consortium that, from the start, actively engages policymakers and other societal stakeholders in co-creating outcomes that respond to end users' needs.

ACHIEVE is aligned with the Work Programme of Cluster 5, Destination 1, "Climate sciences and responses for the transformation towards climate neutrality", as the project directly contributes to advancing knowledge and providing solutions for climate change, specifically on high integrity voluntary climate action. ACHIEVE will develop transition pathways to climate neutrality that integrate voluntary climate action by cities, regions and companies; it will develop novel social science insights for climate action; contribute to a better understanding of sustainability co-benefits and trade-offs; and increase transparency and trust in voluntary climate action by strengthening integrity and making scientific results easily accessible for different stakeholder groups.

Start date: 01-01-2024

End date: 31-01-2028

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1 Introduction

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the ACHIEVE project was created using the online tool DMPONLINE¹ and adheres to the template specified by the European Commission for Horizon Europe projects. This DMP is a living document, expected to undergo updates and revisions throughout the project's lifecycle. The document retains the original template structure, with visible text boxes at the beginning of each section and consistent numbering with the template headings. All the project partners were responsible for creating this document, which the project management office led and facilitated. This file resides in a secure SharePoint server hosted by Radboud University, where project partners have easy access for reference and updates whenever necessary.

¹ <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk>

2 Data summary

Provide a summary of the data addressing the following issues:

1. State the purpose of the data collection/generation
2. Explain the relation to the objectives of the project
3. Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected
4. Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)
5. Specify the origin of the data
6. State the expected size of the data (if known)
7. Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

Climate actions are crucial in climate change adaptation and mitigation. Qualitative and quantitative data from various phases of climate action, from planning, implementing, and reporting, help track the progress of climate action. Like most sustainability challenges, climate action is riddled with many data problems, including the absence of data, obscurity, inconsistency, lack of high quality and difficult data accessibility. Quantitative data specific to climate action include but are not limited to emission data, reduction targets, carbon offsetting, energy consumption, resource usage, financial data, disclosure, reporting and verification. Qualitative data includes narratives, stories, perceptions and attitudes, processes, challenges, engagement, partnerships, resiliency and aspirations. Data and its integrity are central in identifying opportunities to scale high-integrity voluntary climate actions (VCA) towards achieving net zero by 2050. To evaluate and achieve integrity in voluntary climate action, the ACHIEVE project will use existing data and develop new data on climate action.

To assess the integrity of voluntary climate action, we foresee using the following kinds of data, either created during the project or building on existing data. We will collect and curate data on existing voluntary climate action of both non-state and sub-state entities, including businesses, climate initiatives, cities, regions and organisations. Most project partners, who are experts in the research field of voluntary climate action, already have in-house data. Sharing and re-using such data between the partners is stipulated and governed by the Grant Agreement. Table 1 below summarises the type of data foreseen to be used in the project.

Table 1: List of types of data foreseen to be generated and used in the ACHIEVE project.

Types of data	Partners	WP/tasks	Data file type	Data file size
Background information on VCA, profiles of VCA, policies governing VCA locally, nationally, in the EU, and internationally, socio-ecological and economic impacts of VCA	Radboud University, University of Eastern Finland	WP1, 3	Text document, spreadsheets, audio-visual documents	<100MB
Qualitative and quantitative data from interviews, surveys and workshops of VCA stakeholders	Radboud University, Stockholm University, University of Eastern Finland	WP1, 3	Text document, spreadsheets, audio-visual documents	< 100MB
Qualitative and quantitative data from existing or future governance of VCA	Radboud University, University of Eastern Finland	WP1, 2, 3	Spreadsheet	< 100MB
Quantitative and quality data on initiatives relating to the carbon market	Oeko-Institut Radboud University	WP1, 2, 3	Spreadsheet, Text documents	< 100MB
Mitigation goals, membership of VCA initiatives	PBL, Radboud University	WP1, 2, 4	Spreadsheet	< 100MB
Qualitative data on city case studies	Oeko-Institut	WP3	Text documents	< 100MB
Quantitative and qualitative data on companies' climate action and indicators that determine emissions levels, such as location and income	NewClimate Institute, PBL	WP2, 3, 4	Mainly spreadsheets, csv formats	Up to 2GB
Transition pathways/scenario outputs with the integration of VCAs	E3M	WP4	Text documents, spreadsheets	< 100MB

Qualitative data on case studies in Central America	CATIE	WP2	Text documents, spreadsheets	< 100MB
Data related to stakeholder engagement and communication activities of the project such as mailing lists, interview transcripts, survey results, etc.	HOLISTIC / WWF	WP4, WP5	Text documents, spreadsheets	< 1GB

To achieve the objective of the project, we will re-use and make sense of existing data on voluntary climate action gathered by various organisations for more than a decade. These data sets capture commitments, actions, progress and other data related to voluntary climate action. Table 2 lists the data sources and details how project partners will reuse them.

Table 2: List of how project partners will re-use existing data

Data Source	Name of Partner	Data Kind	Data type file	Work package	Data file size
Climate Cooperative Initiatives Database (C-CID)	Radboud University (RU) Stockholm University (SU), University of Eastern Finland (UEF), CATIE, University of Oxford (UOXF)	mixed	.xlsx / currently partly online in RU's Global Data Lab	WP 1-2	Approx. 50 MB
Nature-based-Climate Cooperative Initiatives Database (N-CID)	Radboud University (RU), CATIE	mixed	.xlsx	WP 1-2	Approx. 50 MB
Net Zero tracker	Radboud University,	mixed	.xlsx, .csv	WP1-3	Approx. 2MB

	NewClimate Institute, Stockholm University (SU), University of Eastern Finland (UEF), University of Oxford (UOXF)				
Net Zero Data Public Utility	NewClimate Institute, University of Eastern Finland (UEF)	mixed	.xlsx, .csv	WP2	Up to 100MB
Climate Policy Database	NewClimate Institute, University of Eastern Finland (UEF)	mixed	.xlsx	WP2	Approx. 20MB
CDP Climate Questionnaire	NewClimate Institute, University of Eastern Finland (UEF), PBL	mixed	.xlsx	WP2, 4	Up to 1GB
CCQI Scores	Oeko-Institut	quantitative	.xlsx	WP 2 / WP3	Approx. 210 KB
Voluntary regions and city commitments	PBL	quantitative	.csv/.xlsx	WP4	Up to 100MB

3 FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Outline naming conventions used

Outline the approach towards search keyword

Outline the approach for clear versioning

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

The ACHIEVE project is committed to the Horizon Europe principle of data used to be “as open as possible, as closed as needed”. We intend to make datasets public unless there is a clear reason not to do so. To increase accessibility and data longevity, we will use different platforms to make the data easily accessible to the public. These include Zenodo, the RU repository and the ACHIEVE website. All project outputs will be available on the ACHIEVE website, which will serve as a central resource hub for interested parties to learn more about the project and its deliverables. The website will be online during ACHIEVE’s duration and for at least two years after the project ends. Nevertheless, Zenodo and the RU repository will store all the data produced and used by the project, as these platforms will remain online for the foreseeable future.

While making data publicly available, we will ensure a standard set of metadata that records authors, titles, dates, descriptions, identifiers, and rights for each data set. Wherever applicable, a unique identifier, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), will be used that contains the abovementioned metadata. All project datasets and deliverables will receive a DOI when added in Zenodo, while journal and conference publications will get a DOI from their respective publishers. Metadata will be guided by the Metadata Standards Directory².

² <http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/standards/>

To ensure transparency of file contents and versioning, a readme.txt file accompanying each data set will explain the file naming and versioning approach used. Some data sets may have different requirements, but we follow these standards whenever possible. Furthermore, a set of relevant keywords will accompany the published dataset to increase discoverability.

ACHIEVE	Project name, fixed
D[x.y]	Deliverable identifier, if relevant
[Short Title]	Short descriptor for easy identification, maximum 40 characters
V[Version]	Version number in x.y format, should match the version number with a short description inside the document, such as the Document History table in the beginning of the ACHIEVE report template
[Type]	Describes the type of data (e.g. publication, inventory, etc.)
[Date]	Date in format YYYY-MM-DD
[Status]	Draft, Final, Public, Restricted, Confidential
Underscore	_ marks the end of current field and starts a new field (see example below)
optional	Free text field for internal communication purposes, at the end of the file name, immediately before the extension (e.g. initials of reviewer). This field should not be included in the name of published files.

Example: "ACHIEVE_D7.2_Initial Data Management Plan_v0.3_Report Draft.docx"

3.2 Making data openly accessible:

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

Specify how the data will be made available

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

According to the ACHIEVE Consortium Agreement, each beneficiary can publish their outputs but must get explicit agreement from partners or data providers to publish datasets for open access. The project follows Horizon Europe's "as open as possible, as closed as needed" principle, aiming to make datasets public by default. However, exceptions are allowed, for example, for commercially sensitive data or confidential information from consultations or interviews. In these cases, confidentiality is ensured through informed consent forms, with respondents guaranteed anonymity. If anonymised interview data were to be publicly accessible, respondents would need to provide a second consent.

It is the responsibility of the lead partner of a dataset to:

1. Determine if a data set can be made public, partly or entirely, immediately or after an embargo period.
2. Explain their decisions in the updated version of this Data Management Plan.
3. Ensure that datasets follow the GDPR when applicable.
4. Keep in mind the intellectual property rights of the working data at all times.
5. Ensure that data meet specific standards, if applicable, to make them interoperable.

3.3 Making data interoperable:

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

ACHIEVE will ensure that our published datasets can be understood clearly, even for future users outside this project. To do this, each dataset must have a description explaining how the data was gathered, where it came from, what it means, and how it can be used. This information usually goes in a readme.txt file, as mentioned above, unless there is a better way to include it.

We will try to organise our datasets so they can be combined with other datasets from this project or other sources. Lead partners will check if data standards like the Research Data Alliance (RDA) or similar standards apply to data used in the ACHIEVE project and follow them appropriately. Using common standards and methods in our research fields, we will make sure that datasets can work together smoothly. We will use resources like fairsharing.org to find the proper standards and databases.

We will do the following to ensure the published dataset's interoperability.

- Oeko-Institut will ensure data is available in well-structured tables in easily machine-readable formats (e.g. CSV). Meta-data will be widely available, particularly column descriptions and nomenclatures. Moreover, Oeko-Institut will check if a standard for interoperability is suitable for the data we use and apply it appropriately.
- NewClimate Institute has a policy to make all data publicly available where possible. We generally work with MS Excel. Many of the data tools are available on the NewClimate Institute website³. We make data available in other machine-readable forms, such as downloadable CSV files or through an API.

³ <https://newclimate.org/resources/tools>

- All result data from the modelling activities of the project (PBL, E3M) will be formatted according to the IAMC time-series scenario format⁴. As this format has been extensively used in modelling intercomparisons and assessment reports such as the IPCC AR6, it will make ACHIEVE’s modelling results interoperable within the wider integrated assessment modelling community. The datasets will also be uploaded on the I²AM PARIS platform (HOL), where they can be filtered and downloaded in the same format, further facilitating their use by other modellers.
- CATIE uses standardised data formats that are commonly used and downloadable, such as XML, CSV, and GeoJSON, to allow integration, sharing, and use across different systems and contexts. Comprehensive metadata will be implemented and made available.

3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

Describe data quality assurance processes

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

The project will use the Zenodo repository, RU repository and ACHIEVE website to share non-confidential datasets publicly and, in the case of the two repositories, permanently for the foreseeable future. Zenodo automatically suggests a suitable license for the data. By default, data from the project will be licensed under Creative Commons Share-Alike and Attribution unless there is a good reason not to. Public datasets are expected to be published following the publication of related output(s) and will be formatted accordingly to facilitate reuse by third parties. Any data that is not intended for reuse

⁴ <https://pyam-iamc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/data.html> and <https://nomenclature-iamc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

will be justified in detail in a future version of this DMP. To ensure quality, we will follow a rigorous scientific process, including curating and harmonising data to standards when applicable and publishing them where a third party can reuse the data for the foreseeable future. In some instances, especially for academic publications that are not published as gold open access, we foresee some embargo periods. We aim to publish at least 20 open-access journal articles as stipulated in the Description of Action document.

4 Allocation of resources

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

Describe the costs and potential value of long-term preservation

Outputs and datasets will be published on the Zenodo repository, eliminating extra costs for permanent storage. The ACHIEVE website will either host the data or will provide links to Zenodo. We do not foresee costs other than personnel hours spent researching and managing data and output. Open-source publications of academic articles could incur significant costs, with Article Processing Costs (APCs) ranging from 2,000-10,000 euro. However, the project strategically plans to minimise these costs as best as possible either by publishing with journals that our partners have open-access agreements or applying for co-funding for the open-access publishing cost from the institution or organisation. In addition, ACHIEVE project partners have also accounted for open-access publication fees in their Horizon Europe budget.

Furthermore, project partners will share data, know-how, and information. For example, all partners will have access to CDP data as stipulated in the consortium agreement. To ensure the availability of data on cities and regions' emissions and commitments and the locations of companies, we have budgeted € 25,000 for the project.

Kaustubh Thapa, from Radboud University, will oversee the data management for this project and maintain and update the data management plan as necessary. The project partner leads and work package leaders will be in charge of their data set, as mentioned in Section 2 of the data management plan.

5 Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

All Outputs and datasets will be securely stored in Zenodo. In this state-of-the-art repository, data are securely stored and backed up regularly following the latest data security, protection and recovery protocols.

For data management during the execution of the project, all communication and data are stored securely at Radboud University's SharePoint infrastructure provided by Microsoft and hosted at servers within the European Union. Only project members have access to this data, which is backed up regularly. Each partner is responsible for managing, securing and protecting their data during the project period. A summary of how the project partners back up the data is provided in the following table.

Table 3: Data security implemented in the ACHIEVE project

Name of Partner	Data Security
Radboud University (RU)	<p>Radboud University data will be stored on the Radboud Data Repository of the project where data can be published, safely archived if data cannot be publicly shared, made available to collaborate inside and outside Radboud University, made findable by assigning a digital object identifier, and managed to provide access to view and/or edit data. The Radboud Data Repository complies with data management policies of Radboud University's policy on findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR) of research data.</p> <p>Radboud University will also store raw and processed intermediate data on the science faculty's server, where data is regularly backed-up and access can be controlled.</p>
NewClimate Institute for Climate Policy and Global Sustainability (NCI)	<p>NewClimate data is stored in Microsoft's SharePoint cloud. The servers are located in Germany. Data on SharePoint is encrypted, and access is managed based on user accounts. The data is backed up with HornetSecurity, whose servers are also located in Germany.</p>
Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management (PBL)	<p>The PBL work is divided into three components: 1) data, 2) modelling, analysis, and 3) reporting. Input data is stored in in the Microsoft environment that have regular backups (multiple times per day). Model data and quantitative analysis is under</p>

	version control on either SVN or GitHub. ACHIEVE reporting or literature preparation is done in either dedicated project locations or using the RU SharePoint.
Öko-Institute - Institute for Applied Ecology (OEKO)	During the implementation of the project, Oeko-Institut will store intermediate data on the Oeko-Institut's SharePoint infrastructure, which is facilitated by Microsoft. Data is backed up regularly, and the access is limited to project members.
E3-Modeling (E3M)	E3M is not expected to manage any sensitive or personal data. The project's repository (Radboud Data Repository) will be used for any data exchange between partners of the consortium.
University of Eastern Finland (UEF)	The storing of project data will be supported by University of Eastern Finland's Digital Services (DiPa) and will be backed up on Spersonal LocalDrive storage or secured researcher disk space
Tropical Agricultural Research and Higher Education Center (CATIE)	CATIE's data will be stored in the institutional Microsoft SharePoint cloud, with the access limited to project members. Data will be backed up on CATIE's server.
Stockholm University (SU)	Sunet Drive/Nextcloud is a secure storage solution based on Nextcloud and Sunet's S3 storage in a private cloud. The storage offers the ability to both share and control access to research data within and outside Stockholm University. The provider, Sunet (Swedish University Computer Network), is part of the Swedish Research Council.
University of Oxford (UOXF)	UOXF's data that is used in the project is shared with Radboud University and partners (C-CID Database), storage and management is subject to the same provisions as under RU. UOXF's data related to the Net-Zero Tracker is freely available with attribution under a Creative Commons BY 4.0 License, and is stored and made available through the Net-Zero Tracker platform. The data on net zero commitments is collected from publicly-available data, such as international commitments, laws, governmental policies, entities' websites, corporate annual reports, sustainability reports and press releases.
HOLISTIC (HOL)	HOLISTIC will use its professional instance of Microsoft's SharePoint to store data related to ACHIEVE. This SharePoint instance is hosted in servers within the EU that are compliant

	with GDPR rules and are frequently backed up.
World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)	WWF won't manage sensitive data
CDP Europe (CDP)	CDP Europe will follow the state of the art data security technology and protocol for data management.

Each partner uses a secure data server to store and transfer sensitive data, following their organisational guidelines. As mentioned above, data transfer is via SharePoint, encrypted emails, and equivalent safe transfer methods, some of which are described in the table above.

6 Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

Research activity in the project is guided by organisational guidelines for research with integrity and ethics. For instance, Radboud University's guiding principles⁵ for research with integrity are honesty, diligence, transparency, independence and accountability, which complies with the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and European standards. Furthermore, Radboud University complies with its strict Research Data Management policy⁶. All project activities will comply with international, national and European laws as necessary. Details of the data management policies of partners are listed in Annex I.

⁵ <https://www.ru.nl/en/regulations/radboud-university-code-of-conduct>

⁶ <https://www.ru.nl/en/about-us/policies-and-regulations/research-data-management>

Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

Data Management Policies and Procedures for Project Partners

This section provides specific data management policies and procedures for the partners of the ACHIEVE project, who are diverse in their size, mission, function, and geographic location and play various roles in the project.

Annex I: Data Management Policy and Procedures

Table 4: Data Management Policy and Procedures for ACHIEVE partners.

Partner	Data Management Policy and Procedure
Radboud University (RU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data policies are listed on the Radboud University Research Data website⁷ and include <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ General research data management policy ○ Findability, accessibility, interoperable and reusable of research data • The Radboud Institute of Biological and Environmental Sciences also has an additional, more specific research data management policy, which guides research data management of Radboud University employees in this project⁸. • Radboud University researchers follow Dutch and EU regulations including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The GDPR and the Dutch GDPR Implementation Act ○ The Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (VSNU, 2018)
NewClimate Institute for Climate Policy and Global Sustainability (NCI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data management policy of NewClimate Institute⁹ • NewClimate Institute has an internal procedure to comply with the national (Germany), European and international standards which includes documentation of data management procedures and regular checks.
Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management (PBL)	<p>PBL has a policy on research data that ensures all data should be stored on secured storage, protected against unauthorized use and loss of data. It uses facilities that include two-factor authorization and back-up features. For the IMAGE model, that is used in this project, more specific data management can be found in the IMAGE strategy¹⁰.</p>
Öko-Institute - Institute for Applied Ecology (OEKO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data policies can be found in the Oeko-Institut's Code of Conduct https://www.oeko.de/fileadmin/institut/OEI-Code-of-Conduct.pdf. This includes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Policy regarding open science practices and research data management ○ Policy regarding the responsible handling of

⁷ <https://www.ru.nl/rdm/vm/policy-documents/>

⁸ <https://www.ru.nl/ribes/organisation/data-management/>

⁹ <https://newclimate.org/about-us/legal-notice>

¹⁰ <https://www.pbl.nl/en/publications/the-image-strategy-document-2022-2027>

	<p>international standards in terms of data management.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Specifically, all research activities and software development of the company are performed in line with the GDPR rules.• Any sensitive data collected for and by these activities (e.g., visitors' data on HOLISTIC's websites) are strictly used for their intended use (e.g., anonymised reports of visitors' activity) and are retained only for a minimum amount of time.
World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• WWF Colombia complies with the organizational data policy¹².
CDP Europe (CDP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• CDP data management policy is guided by institutional guideline put in place by designated security official and security team responsible for data security and data management.

¹² [https://www.wwf.org.co/politica de tratamiento de datos/](https://www.wwf.org.co/politica_de_tratamiento_de_datos/)